

Developing Teamwork Skills among Civil Servants through 'Teambuilding'

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Introduction

In public administration, improving the representation and executive mechanisms of local government requires effective communication skills, teamwork, the ability to inspire subordinates, assess conflicts accurately, and find solutions. Leadership qualities are of great importance. Effective use of human resources in management, addressing emerging problems, fostering creative thinking, and adopting a systematic approach are crucial for developing soft skills.

Methods

In our Constitution, it is established that the Councils of People's Deputies in regions, districts, and cities (except for cities subordinate to districts) are representative bodies of state power. Additionally, the Presidential Decree No. PF-158 of September 11, 2023, on the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, approved the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy. The second priority direction, titled "Ensuring the Rule of Law, Organizing Public Administration in Service of the People," outlines the goal of increasing the efficiency of addressing public problems through expanding communication with the people. This involves abolishing the practice of registering appeals in paper form within government agencies and organizations, allowing electronic submission of appeals through mobile applications, ensuring that at least 80% of appeals are addressed locally, reducing the proportion of repeated appeals by at least two times, and creating a public-centered system that resolves social and economic problems at the local level. Additionally, the decree sets the task of providing 100% opportunities for citizens to participate remotely in video communications during meetings with officials of executive authorities at the regional level.

Results

The implementation of these priority tasks places a high level of responsibility on local representative bodies. This, in turn, requires improving the methods of communication with the public, addressing mutual problems systematically, enhancing the emotional intelligence of public officials, resolving conflicts, and strengthening leadership qualities. It also calls for innovative methods and tools for resolving the social and economic issues of the population.

The importance of *teambuilding* in developing teamwork skills is significant. This concept is derived from the English words meaning "to build a team" or "to work with a team." Today, all top-tier companies and organizations organize corporate teambuilding training for their employees, focused on building teams, fostering teamwork, and developing group cohesion. The primary goal is to improve interpersonal relationships among employees, create a positive psychological climate within the team, increase employees' loyalty to the employer company and colleagues, encourage a sense of both enjoyment and responsibility toward work, and cultivate and develop individual characteristics.

As a result, employees' work efficiency, motivation, and commitment increase, which, in turn, elevates the company's human resource potential. Employees develop professional competence, mutual support skills, assistance, and effective teamwork abilities. For the company, this means having a reliable, dependable, and resilient team that can adapt to any situation. These training sessions generally combine both theoretical knowledge and practical exercises.

In organizing team activities effectively, constructiveness, cooperation, mutual influence, and solidarity are of crucial importance. Mutual cooperation and solidarity manifest in shaping a unified strategy within an organization and facilitating joint activities through information exchange. Mutual cooperation is the process by which objects (or subjects) influence each other directly or indirectly, creating interdependencies and relationships between them. The mutual influence of individuals is a necessary element of any collaborative activity.

In studying the content of mutual cooperation, different perspectives express this situation as follows:

- ✓ The process of influence, forms of communication, and their development;
- ✓ Coordination;
- ✓ Unity of activities and its characteristic;
- ✓ Personal communication.

It should be noted that mutual cooperation is closely tied to the category of "communication." In society and within any team, mutual cooperation among individuals cannot occur without communication. Communication can occur directly within the scope of activities, regulate those activities, and serve as a necessary means for mutual influence.

The following social-psychological types of mutual cooperation can be distinguished:

- Solidarity: Partners assist each other, actively contributing to the achievement of each individual's goals and the overall goals of the joint activity.
- Conflict: Partners oppose each other, hindering the achievement of each individual's goals.
- Avoidance of mutual cooperation: Partners try to avoid influencing each other.
- One-sided support: One participant contributes to achieving the other's individual goals, while the other avoids mutual relations with them.
- One-sided opposition: One participant obstructs the other's goals, while the other avoids relations with the first participant.

- Counteracting influence: One participant tries to help the other, while the other actively resists their assistance.
- Compromised mutual influence: Both partners assist each other and resist at the same time.

A necessary condition for fully developing an individual's moral potential in society is mutual responsibility and the high standards individuals set for one another. Of course, none of the aspects mentioned above can be denied or altered. The existence and stability of a culture of mutual attention, respect for individuals, high internal discipline, integrity, and responsibility, along with demanding standards for both others and oneself, harmonized with a spirit of friendliness—these are the key characteristics of a healthy moral and psychological environment.

A healthy psychological environment is one of the decisive factors in achieving successful work in all areas of social relations. It is an essential condition for shaping lifestyle and personality.

Discussion

American psychologist R. Likert, based on his research, defines the characteristics of an effective team. These indicators highlight advanced team activities and the dynamic processes within the team. Thus, an effective team is one where:

1. Team members have the skills to perform all types of roles and functions. Both employees and leaders can participate as executors to shape the necessary relationships in the team.
2. The team operates over a long period, and during this time, peaceful and businesslike relations form among the members.
3. The team environment is pleasant for its members, and each member maintains positive relations with others.
4. Team members keep the team's activities confidential and have high mutual trust.
5. Existing values and goals ensure team cohesion. Team members continuously improve and develop these values.
6. Employees perform interrelated functions, ensuring that values and goals are harmonized.
7. The team members are inclined to accept important values for the team.
8. Team members respect the team's values and strive to implement them. Each team member expends all their energy to achieve the team's primary goal and expects the same from others.
9. All mutual relations, decision-making, and problem-solving occur in a cordial atmosphere. Opinions, evaluations, and criticisms are offered with the intent to assist. A certain level of respect forms when helping each other. Leaders perceive the environment in the team based on current principles. Therefore, highly structured teams are characterized by a mood of collaboration rather than competition.
10. The team helps each member develop their abilities and opportunities.
11. Each team member voluntarily and openly accepts the team's goals, hoping the team will provide favorable conditions.
12. The team leader and members believe that every employee can achieve their goals. In this environment, an employee's inner strength and capabilities are directed toward the goal.
13. When needed, team members offer help to their colleagues in pursuit of mutual benefit. Mutual assistance is a characteristic of a highly structured team.
14. A high-level team creates a creative environment within the team.
15. The team accepts a constructive rule of obedience, knowing when and how to use it for specific

goals.

16. Team members are capable of exchanging information in a sincere and open manner, sharing relevant information related to the team's values.
17. The team fully utilizes its communication system in achieving its goal.
18. Each team member takes an interest in any information related to the issue at hand.
19. The motivation for mutual influence among team members is strong in a highly effective team.
20. The team's dynamic process in highly effective teams also strongly influences the leader.
21. Since team members have the ability to influence each other's actions, the team adapts quickly to any situation.
22. In highly effective teams, when decisions are made, employees face new situations with confidence and feel safe, as each team member feels their own interests are protected due to the clarity of the team's principles and goals.
23. In a highly effective team, the principles of selection and election are implemented.

In conclusion the process of team formation is one that requires advanced management skills. To accomplish this, it is essential not only to have well-chosen, highly skilled specialists but also individuals who are eager to work together as a cohesive team.

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